

CULTURAL CONFLICT: THE PROCESS OF CULTURAL IDENTITY CHANGE IN THE CIVILIZATION

Author: *Anwar Sadad and Fathur Masduki*

Abstract: Much is made of the occurrence of culture shock for expatriates but little discussion occurs on the reverse but oftentimes more severe shock, that of returning to your home culture after a time away. In fact the majority of people who experience it are not even aware of its existence, even though it's occurrence can physically and emotionally disrupt your life. The occurrence and effects of culture shock are well documented but less is known about reverse culture shock, being largely unrecognized by most as even a possibility. Your time away from your home culture influences you more than you realize, and reverse culture shock can be a significant factor in repatriation.

Keyword: *Culture Shock; Cultural Conflict; Identity; Civilization; Ideology;*

Introductio

I can remember three distinct instances in my life where I experienced this phenomenon. Each case was different. The first was a summer spent living with the family of a college friend in Mexico. The second was a summer spent traveling and studying in India. The third was a year teaching in Puerto Rico immediately upon returning from my trip to India.

I personally feel that the degree to which reverse culture shock occurs depends primarily on four factors: the age at which the experience occurs, the length of time you have been away from your home culture, the degree to which the foreign culture is different from your home culture, and whether it is your first experience in a new culture or only one in a series of numerous such occurrences in your life. Each of these factors have a different degree of effect, but taken together create a combination of factors that facilitates the occurrence of reverse culture shock.

Age. Youth is a time when new things are not only easily accepted but oftentimes eagerly looked forward to. I think both the severity of culture shock and reverse culture shock is therefore less noticed by this group. The older generation is more socialized into their home cultural tradition and in most cases less able to quickly adapt to change. Over my three months in Mexico (my first foreign experience), I noticed the differences, but actually looked forward to the next exciting, unexpected occurrence. I talked about my experiences for months, but my major need when I got back to the U.S. was my craving for a hot dog and a heaping plate of mashed potatoes. So much for reverse culture shock!

Length of Time. Both my first Mexico and India experiences lasted about three months. There was sufficient time to start adapting to the new environments, but not enough time to become completely acclimatized to the new culture.

Extent of Cultural Differences. Reverse culture shock is greatest when the language and culture of your host country is dramatically different from your own. For that reason, it was much more difficult to adapt to the changes induced in my thinking while in India than it was when I was in Mexico.

Number of expatriate experiences You have had. There seems to be a direct correlation between the number of different cultural destinations you have experienced and your ability to adapt to additional ones or to the effects of reverse culture shock upon your return.

Like culture shock, reverse culture shock affects different individuals to a different degree. Being aware of the possibility of its occurrence upon your return home may not stop it, but will help you understand what is happening to you.

Discussion

Cultural Conflict: the beginning of civilization

As a mediator for the Equal Employment Opportunity Commission, I have noticed a significant number of discrimination complaints being initiated by new arrivals (recent immigrants). An organization's culture may be different from the cultures of some employees from other countries. Expression of these cultural differences on the job can lead to misunderstandings, conflict, and discrimination charges. Here are a few suggestions for lessening the probability of such complaints.

The following is an example of the potential of cultural differences to lead to conflict. Asians, Hispanics, and some Europeans may not initiate tasks without specific instruction because this is considered a challenge to the supervisor's authority. American supervisors may view this perceived lack of initiative as laziness or lack of self-confidence. In this situation, it may be helpful to work with an informal group leader of the employees' culture or with a community agency representing the employees' culture group. They can help explain to the employee the American way of doing things. Using a group leader or cultural organization as a resource communicates the supervisor's respect for the culture. It will help in getting the job done.

Be mindful that terminology used by a cultural group may have different meanings and may create misunderstandings depending on the speakers and the listener's cultural perspectives. In those situations, it might be helpful to employ informational feedback that

requires restating in the listeners own words what the speaker has said and the listener uses to show that she understands what is being conveyed.

"Cultural myopia" is a belief that one's particular culture is appropriate in all situations and relevant to all others. It can lead to conflict. Another concept that can trigger conflict is, "ethnocentrism". Ethnocentrism is looking at and valuing situations only from your cultural or ethnic perspective, and all other perspectives are scaled and rated with reference to it. Everyone is ethnocentric to a degree but being aware that you are is the beginning of appreciating and valuing other perspectives and reducing the potential for conflict.

Communicating stereotypes about anyone or the cultural group they belong to can and will eventually result in conflicts with members of that group. This is true even if one is communicating with one's own cultural identity group. In work settings, those stereotypical comments tend to find their way to members of the other cultural groups and create barriers and unnecessary conflict with others. Be mindful of any stereotypes you may spread and stop spreading them. If others are expressing stereotypes to you in a work group, one way to stop them is simply to confront them with a statement that what they said is a stereotype. You can helpfully point out that their assessment does not ring true for the whole group or individuals in that group. You can tell them that you would appreciate it if they would deal with each group member as in individual first.

Increasing the quality and frequency of your communications with others from different cultural, ethnic, religious, etc. perspectives is a huge key to reducing the potential of cross-cultural conflict. We have to be mindful that our initial encounters with others who are different is usually filled with anxiety and that this is a common reaction. We can use the energy of that anxiety to begin to open communication with others thereby reducing our and their anxiety and the potential for cross-cultural conflict. Remaining open-minded and flexible in our contact with others will be helpful in building supportive bridges to other cultures.

The Process of Cultural Identity Change: Separation, Limen and Re-Aggregation Applied to Migrants

After studying Ndembu culture, Turner went on to apply the concept of separation, limen and re- aggregation to other societies, including contemporary Western industrialized societies. There, he found the ritual stages operating in such unlikely areas as modern art, literature, theatre, sports and other recreational pastimes. Similarly, it is possible to take Turner's views and apply them to cultural identity issues to migrants in Diaspora. Upon comparison, it is evident that the immigration process mimics the three stages of separation, limen and re-aggregation.

Most migrants tend to reside between two cultures. Like the Ndembu initiates, they have been removed from their culture and society in a process resembling Turner's stage of separation. Migrants have also been transplanted into another country where they are expected to assimilate or re-aggregate into the new culture, complete with a new status, role and responsibilities. However, it is evident that many migrants are unable to do so. In many cases, re-aggregation is not fully achieved due to such things as immigration status problems. With no legal status and no access to certain privileges within the host

country, (such as the right to work or receive health care) undocumented migrants have great difficulty laying down roots and assimilating into the host culture. The same is the case for many asylum seekers whose cases are still pending. Xenophobia and racism can also prevent re-aggregation. The worse the xenophobia is within the host country, the harder it becomes for a foreigner to attach psychologically and economically to the society and develop a sense of belonging. As well, culture shock and grief issues that involve mourning the homeland can delay the process of adapting to the host culture and completing assimilation. Thus, being unable to fully participate in the new society while also being unable to return to the old society leaves many migrants in "cultural limbo." Similar to the limen state that Turner describes, migrants are neither here nor there—they are stuck "betwixt and between" cultures, lacking in cultural identity. They are isolated and socially "invisible," possessing no cultural status—a case that is especially true for undocumented migrants and asylum seekers.

In rites of passage, the liminal phase is intended to be a temporary condition. It is not possible for an individual to live permanently in a state of limen, without some sort of identity. Lack of identity is confusing and causes psychological discord as well as the inability to fully function within a society. However, as we have seen, many migrants are forced to indefinitely reside "betwixt and between" cultures. What is the solution for them?

Conclusion

For many undocumented migrants working in the Diaspora, the solution lies in keeping a primarily homeland cultural identity. Because xenophobia is so high in some host countries, assimilation is difficult. Moreover, many migrants in some host countries tend to be seasonal laborers—agricultural workers who return home during the off-season. Subsequently, it is simpler for these migrants to label themselves as "foreign seasonal workers," rather than new citizens of the host country—their cultural identity can remain unequivocally that of their homeland and they encounter no identity crisis.

But what about the rest of the Diaspora, who live further abroad and do not get the opportunity to visit home as frequently? And what about permanent residents or political refugees who have no option but to reside indefinitely in their host country? These members of

the Diaspora live in a cultural "limbo land," forced to struggle with two different cultural identities. The issue is further complicated by the fact that many in the Diaspora plan to migrate home some day.

Those who plan to eventually return home would likely attempt to maintain their national identity throughout their residence abroad. Yet to do so can be extremely challenging. Time spent in Diaspora often unintentionally drags on for years or even decades. Immigrants in these circumstances often find themselves forced to make a choice between two cultures--a particularly painful and confusing dilemma. However, as the following section will demonstrate, the answer perhaps lies not in choosing one culture over the other, but in creating a new cultural identity based upon cultural integration and time.

References

- Aldyan, R. A., Warty, W., & Marimin, M. (2019). " Ngalab Berkah" on the Tradition to Open Luwur the Sunan Kudus Tomb. *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, 6(4), 156-165.
- Andayani, T. R. (2019, March). Conflict in Javanese Adolescents' Friendship and its Resolution Strategy. In *4th ASEAN Conference on Psychology, Counselling, and Humanities (ACPCH 2018)*. Atlantis Press.
- Arno, A., & Dissanayake, W. (2019). *The news media in national and international conflict*. Routledge.
- Brulle, R. J., & Norgaard, K. M. (2019). Avoiding cultural trauma: climate change and social inertia. *Environmental Politics*, 28(5), 886-908.
- Dewi, E. W., Drajadi, N. A., & Yunus, M. M. (2019). Exploring Intonations in Sesame Street's Puppet Shows: A Phonological Perspective. *Issues in Language Studies*, 8(2), 32-47.
- Favre, M., Swedlow, B., & Verweij, M. (2019). A cultural theory and model of power relations. *Journal of Political Power*, 12(2), 245-275.
- Fredriksson, E. (2019). Kidnapped Cultural Heritage?: A Cultural Analysis on the Conflict about Cultural Heritage Among Cultural and Political Actors.
- Gennaioli, N., & Tabellini, G. (2019). Identity, Beliefs, and Political Conflict. *Available at SSRN 3300726*.
- Giavazzi, F., Petkov, I., & Schiantarelli, F. (2019). Culture: Persistence and evolution. *Journal of Economic Growth*, 24(2), 117-154.
- Habibi, H. (2016). PERAN KI DALANG BASARI (1950-2003) DALAM PERKEMBANGAN ISLAM DI GEGESIK CIREBON. *Jurnal Tamaddun: Jurnal Sejarah dan Kebudayaan Islam*, 1(2).
- Habibi, H. (2018). Protecting National Identity Based On The Value Of Nation Local Wisdom. *International Journal of Malay-Nusantara Studies*, 1(2), 24-40.
- Haynes, J. (2020). *Religion, Conflict and Post-Secular Politics*. Routledge.

- Hugo, J., & Ambrose, T. (2019). The Future of Languages and A Cultural Immersion.
- Luttmer, E. F., & Singhal, M. (2011). Culture, context, and the taste for redistribution. *American Economic Journal: Economic Policy*, 3(1), 157-79.
- Lam, K. C., & Sukato, N. (2019, April). Perception of Conflict: A Cross-cultural Comparison between Hong Kong Chinese and Thais. In *The 1st CHINA-ASEAN International Conference 2019: Insight to Chinese and ASEAN's Experience and Adaptation* (pp. 96-109). Dhurakij Pundit University.
- Maya, L. (2019). GLOBALIZATION: A MIXTURE OF CULTURES AND DISADVANTAGING DEVELOPING COUNTRIES.
- Nguyen, P. M., Terlouw, C., & Pilot, A. (2006). Culturally appropriate pedagogy: the case of group learning in a Confucian Heritage Culture context. *Intercultural Education*, 17(1), 1-19.
- Raj, A., & Silverman, J. (2002). Violence against immigrant women: The roles of culture, context, and legal immigrant status on intimate partner violence. *Violence against women*, 8(3), 367-398.
- Rudolph, L. I. (2019). The media and cultural politics. In *India Votes* (pp. 159-179). Routledge.
- Russell, J. (2019). The Culture of Narcissism: Cultural Dilemmas, Language Confusion and The Formation of Social Identity.
- Zartman, I. W. (2019). Democracy and Islam: The Cultural Dialectic. In *I William Zartman: A Pioneer in Conflict Management and Area Studies* (pp. 151-160). Springer, Cham.